

DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR AND METHODS OF CORRECTING THEM

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Abstract: *This article deals with difficulties in teaching English grammar and the ways of solving this problem. There are given important information about methods of teaching English grammar and sentence structure between English and Uzbek languages.*

Key words: *English grammar, article, dictionary, inductive, deductive, explicit*

The first president I.A. According to Karimov's opinion, in order to master his profession perfectly and to be able to compete on a global scale, it is necessary for him to be able to understand a foreign language. Therefore, in accordance with the decisions of first president of Uzbekistan on December 10, 2012 on measures to further improve the organization of foreign languages, teaching foreign languages to the young generation is increasingly being strengthened. As we know from history, English and Uzbek languages belong to different language families. This causes language-related, i.e. lexical, pronunciation-related, phonetic, and grammatical difficulties for language learners. Let's talk about grammatical difficulties here. According to the rates given in the dictionaries, grammar is a system of rules and principles followed in the construction of oral and written

speech. Some linguists defined grammar as the rules that make up the structure of language.

The following difficulties can be encountered in teaching English grammar in secondary schools: in contrast to Uzbek, English has strict sentence structure, the presence of incorrect verbs, articles and prepositions, as well as the abundance of tenses. Because the grammar of the language is a unique complex system, if the student does not have good grammatical knowledge and skills of the target language, he will not be able to fully express his thoughts, he will have difficulty in speaking, writing and translating. Teaching this to students requires more research and pedagogical skills from teachers. He teaches grammar taking into account the age and psychological state of the students. Younger students may find grammar rules boring and difficult. Therefore, various interesting games and spoons can be used to teach them grammar. For example, What color is it? What is your name? through spoons, students can ask about colors and their names and organize their answers. It is appropriate to teach grammar in an easier and simpler way to older students. It is also important to reinforce the given topic through exercises by clearly explaining it. Another difficulty in teaching grammar is the article problem. Due to the fact that this subject does not exist in the Uzbek language, problems may arise in the students' learning. At this time, the teacher should clearly explain this topic and explain the indefinite article a/ an in one, one meaning, and the definite article the in one, explaining and distinguishing these meanings. Also, if it is repeatedly reinforced with the help of examples, it is possible to gradually eliminate problematic situations regarding the article.

Another issue students face is the difficulty in using these tenses in writing and speaking. As mentioned above, unlike other subjects, the number of tenses in English is more, so the reader gets a certain confusion in reducing these tenses. In

order to prevent such situations, the teacher can first clearly explain the names of the tenses and the differences between them, and also use different role-playing games so that the students can keep it in practice. For example, if we consider that the teacher has taught three tense rules to the students during the lessons: present simple, past simple, and future simple, he can use this mobile month to strengthen them through exercises. The teacher calls three of the students to the board and tells them to choose one of the three tenses and demonstrate this tense through actions, and the rest of the students have to find this tense. Or you can use other interesting games. For example, in the present continuous tense, we use this month. The teacher tells the students to close their eyes and imagine themselves in a place of their choice and asks the following questions: where are they?, what are they doing? possible This game aims to develop the skills of keeping sentences in the present continuous tense. We can strengthen the simple present tense through the following game. The teacher calls one of the students and asks "What do you usually like to do?" The student answers the teacher without hearing others. The rest of the students try to find out what he likes by asking questions. For example, the following questions can be asked: Do you like to swim? Do you like to read a book? Do you like dancing? Through games like these, grammar teaching can be effective and prevent possible complications. Grammatical material can be taught without learning special rules. This approach to teaching grammar is called the implicit approach. Organizing grammar teaching through special rules was not an explicit approach (from the French verb expliciter). Thus, the formation of skills and competences in grammatical material is carried out by two different approaches and methods with certain positive and negative aspects. Methodist J. J. Jalolov studies the explicit approach to the formation of grammatical skills in two ways: 1) deductive method 2) inductive method.

It is more effective to use the inductive method in teaching language grammar. It is also important for the teacher to use the mother tongue in teaching the students English grammar and for them to remember it. Another scientist, H. Palmer, believes that 10% of lessons should be in the native language, and the rest should be organized in a foreign language, while another scientist, B.V. Belyayev said that 5- 15% of the lesson should be in the native language and the rest in the foreign language being organized. To sum up the above points, every English language teacher should be a highly qualified pedagogue, a master of his profession, and of course, have a deep knowledge of grammar. In the process of teaching grammar, teachers should pay attention to each student and be able to anticipate possible difficulties and find ways to overcome them. It is worth mentioning that, as an interesting and effective way to teach grammar to students, all of the above-mentioned activities should be done by the teacher first explaining the grammatical material and then using them to clarify and strengthen the topic.

References:

1. I.A. Karimov Serving for the happiness, prosperity and future of our Motherland is the highest happiness T. Uzbekistan. 2015.
2. J. Jalolov. Methodology of teaching English, "Teacher" publishing house. Tashkent.
3. D.S. Dzhuzbayeva. "Let's learn English through games"-T.:Uzbekistan Academy of Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic, 2015.
4. Pendidikan Guru Kampus Dato' Razali Ismail "Teaching English grammar in Malaysian primary schools" Manual for short course.